

Subject 1: Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis on Risk Factors for Sporadic Food-Borne Illnesses

Part IV: Yersiniosis

Ursula Gonzales-Barron and Vasco Cadavez
CIMO Mountain Research Centre, School of Agriculture, Polytechnic Institute of Braganza,
Portugal

On request from the French Agency for Food, Environmental and Occupational Health and Safety (ANSES) in coordination with Pauline Kooh and Moez Sanaa

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The quality assessment stage of case-control and cohort studies for human yersiniosis was passed by 14 primary studies investigating only sporadic yersiniosis, which were conducted between 1987 and 2010. From these, three case-control studies investigated exposures in children/infants, while twelve case-control studies focused on the broad mixed population. These primary studies provided 165 ORs categorised for meta-analysis, being 81% of the meta-analytical data produced by primary research from Finland (55 ORs), Norway (30 ORs), New Zealand (25 ORs) and Germany (23 ORs). Six primary studies employed a matched experimental design and produced a total of 81 matched ORs, while the other eight primary studies made use of an unmatched or frequency matched design, producing the other 84 ORs. One-hundred and three reported ORs were not adjusted by any confounder, while 62 ORs were adjusted by using either Mantel-Haenzel method or logistic regressions. The logistic regressions (conditional 50 ORs and unconditional 62 ORs) were the most widely used models, producing 68% of the data. After methodological quality assessment, three case-control studies were marked as being below standards, which yielded a total of 30 potentially-biased ORs. With regards to the risk factor classes, sporadic illness investigations focused more on the multiple pathways of exposure (149 ORs) than on host specific factors (9) and travel (7).

Very limited or no data were available in the literature for risk categories such as recreational water, recent use of antibiotics, recent use of antiacids, chronic diseases, and consumption of eggs, beverages, grains, seafood and dairy. Hence, the significance of these sources as potential vehicles of transmission of yersiniosis could not be appraised. Among the data partitions having sufficient data to be meta-analysed, the most important risk factor for acquiring yersiniosis was the host-specific factor of “other medical conditions”, which grouped together recurrent gastrointestinal conditions and laparotomy in the mixed population, and malnutrition in children (overall OR=5.18; 95% CI: 3.36 – 7.98).

International travel (overall OR=2.26; 95% CI: 0.76 – 6.69) in the mixed population ranked second in importance. Lack of wastewater treatment (overall OR=2.25; 95% CI: 1.41 – 3.57) and farmers' occupational exposure to animals (overall OR=2.07; 95% CI: 1.16 – 3.71) turned out to be at least as important sources of transmission of yersiniosis as the most known exposure of pork meat consumption (overall OR=1.99; 95% CI: 1.79 – 2.21) in the mixed population. Children, however, appeared more susceptible of becoming infected by consuming pork meat (overall OR=3.42; 95% CI: 1.89 – 6.17) than the mixed population. In the mixed population, drinking untreated water posed a greater risk of yersiniosis (overall OR=1.77; 95% CI: 1.23 – 2.53) than the animal pathways of contact with birds and mice (overall OR=1.43; 95% CI: 0.82 – 2.50), pets (overall OR=1.37; 95% CI: 0.79 – 2.39) and farm animals (overall OR=1.22; 95% CI: 0.26 – 5.63). In the children population, consumption of processed meat (overall OR=2.45; 95% CI: 1.23 – 4.87) and exposure to sandbox and baby's dummy (overall OR=1.58; 95% CI: 0.99 – 2.54) were significant pathways of transmission of yersiniosis, yet they came second and third in importance, respectively, after consumption of pork meat.

Food classes that can be considered to have a minor or marginal association with yersiniosis ranked as: dishes eaten out (overall OR=1.36; 95% CI: 0.80 – 2.31), other (non-specified) meats (overall OR=1.31; 95% CI: 0.89 – 1.92), fast-food (overall OR=1.23; 95% CI: 0.98 – 1.53), poultry (overall OR= 1.09; 95% CI: 0.97 – 1.22), roots/legumes (overall OR=1.08; 95% CI: 0.73 – 1.60) and processed meats (overall OR=1.03; 95% CI: 0.97 – 1.10), whereas routes of exposure that, on meta-analysis, did not act as vehicles of transmission of yersiniosis were: fruits (overall OR=0.99; 95% CI: 0.99 – 1.00), beef (overall OR=0.94; 95% CI: 0.87 – 1.02), other red meats (overall OR=0.98; 95% CI: 0.90 – 1.07) and vegetables (overall OR=0.64; 95% CI: 0.44 – 0.94). Finally, in comparison to people who reported having eaten *simply* pork (or other meats), people who ate *undercooked* pork (or other undercooked meats) had their odds of acquiring yersiniosis increased by a factor of 2.945 (95% CI: 2.380 – 3.640), while those who consumed *raw* pork (or other raw meats) had the probability of illness increased by a significantly higher factor of 3.869 times (95% CI: 2.130 – 7.029) that of the base scenario.

3. Results

3.4 *Yersinia enterocolitica*

3.4.1 *Descriptive statistics*

In the systematic review of risk factors pertaining to human infection with *Yersinia enterocolitica*, a total of 807 bibliographic sources were identified using the defined keywords in the five search engines, from which only 33 passed the full assessment for eligibility comprising case-control/case and cohort studies from both sporadic illnesses and outbreaks (Figure 1). A total of 19 fully-documented case-control studies investigated the source(s) of outbreaks and were kept in the JabRef file as their data can be readily extracted. In this study, meta-analysis was undertaken using 14 primary studies focused on sporadic disease (Figure 1). These published studies were conducted between 1987 and 2010. Table 1 compiles a list of the case-control studies along with their main features.

The eligible studies jointly provided 165 categorised odds-ratios for meta-analysis. A total of 66 ORs were retrieved from 8 case-control studies performed before the year 2000, while 99 ORs were excerpted from 6 case-control studies undertaken after 2000. The majority of primary studies investigated human yersiniosis caused by undifferentiated serogroups (9 case-control studies) and O:3 (4 studies), producing 72% of the meta-analytical data (Figure 2, top right). The countries whose case-control studies contributed the largest body of results for sporadic yersiniosis were Finland (55 ORs), Norway (30 ORs), New Zealand (25 ORs) and Germany (23 ORs), which all together constituted ~81% of the meta-analytical data (Figure 2, top left). Twelve case-control studies investigated pathways of exposure in adult or mixed population, while only three case-control studies had children as the target population. The only primary study investigating determinants of disease in both children and mixed population was that of Rosner et al. (2012) (Table 1). Whereas 80% of the ORs originated from exposures evaluated in the mixed/adult population, 20% of the ORs were quantified from ill children cases. (Figure 2, bottom left). As a rule, because of their distinct routes of exposure, the ORs for children and mixed populations were not joined in a single meta-analysis model, but in separate meta-analyses. Data from both populations were merged only when the ORs belonging to the children population were too few to run a separate meta-analysis model.

In all of the primary studies, the cases of yersiniosis were laboratory-confirmed. Six case-control studies employed a matched experimental design and produced a total of 81 categorised ORs (49% of the data). While only 8 ORs were computed in multivariate analysis, 73 were obtained in univariate analysis. ORs from matched designs were mostly estimated using UL (20) and CL (50) and only some of them by MH (3) and the simple chi-square test (8). From the case-control studies that used an unmatched or frequency-matched design (8 studies), 72 ORs were computed in univariate analysis while only 12 in multivariate analysis. Half the ORs from unmatched designs were estimated using chi-square (42 Os) while the other half using UL (42 ORs). Bringing together the matched and unmatched designs, 103 extracted ORs were not adjusted by any confounder (crude ORs), while 62 ORs were adjusted mostly using logistic regressions.

Figure 1. Flow chart of literature search for case-control studies of yersiniosis
*Records kept in JabRef with PDFs files annexed

During methodological quality assessment, three case-control studies were marked as being possibly affected by selection bias (Table 1). In Quoqa et al. (2011) and Wilson et al. (1989), cases of yersiniosis were compared against infected controls had diarrhoea caused by other gastrointestinal infections. As it is not clear whether these controls shared routes of exposure with the case patients, the ORs extracted from these studies were marked as having potential

for bias. The OR measures from Satterhwaite et al. (1999) were assigned the potential-for-bias status because the statistical model was poorly explained. These three case-control studies provided 30 potentially-biased ORs whose influence on the meta-analysed OR estimates was appraised by means of the Cook's distance. With regards to the risk factor classes, sporadic illness investigations focused much more on the multiple pathways of transmission (149 ORs) than on host specific factors (9 ORs) or travel (7 ORs) (Figure 3). General information on the distribution of the number of ORs available for meta-analysis is presented in Figure 3 by study design, type of analysis, model, type of odds-ratio, year category and potential for bias status.

Figure 2. Distribution of the number of odds-ratios (y-axis) extracted from case-control studies of sporadic human infection with *Yersinia enterocolitica* by country (top left), serogroup (top right), population type (bottom left) and type of risk factor (bottom right)

Figure 3. Pie-diagrams of the number of odds-ratios extracted from case-control studies of sporadic yersiniosis by design (top left), analysis type (top right), model type (middle left), odds-ratio type (middle right), year category - 2000 (bottom left) and assigned potential for bias (bottom right)

Table 1. Characteristics of case-control/cohort studies investigating sources of sporadic human yersiniosis included in the meta-analysis

Study ID	Country	Study period	Population	Study & Design	Analysis & Model*	# cases/controls	Quality
Boqvist et al. 2009	Sweden	2004	Children <6 y/o	Matched	Uni-UL Multi-UL	117 cases 339 controls	Good
Cherchi et al. 1995	Italy	1993-1994	Mixed	Prospective cohort, UM	Uni-Chi	16 cases 228 controls	Good
Hansen et al. 2006	Denmark	2006	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni-Chi	129 cases 165 controls	Good
Huovinen et al. 2010	Finland	2006	Mixed	Matched	Uni-CL	54 3-4/O:3 or 2/O:9 133 controls 98 Biotype 1A 251 controls	Good
Ostroff et al. 1992	Norway	1988-1990	Mixed	Matched	Uni-MH	66 O:3 131 controls	Good
Ostroff et al. 1994	Norway	1988-1990	Mixed	Matched	Uni-CL Multi-CL	67 O:3 132 controls	Good
Qouqa et al. 2011	Palestine	2010	Children <12 y/o	Matched	Uni-Chi Multi-UL	16 cases 128 controls	Good
						16 cases 144 GI controls	Poor
Rosner et al. 2012	Germany	2009-2010	Children Mixed	Unmatched	Uni-UL Multi-UL	571 cases 1798 controls	Good
Saebo et al. 1994	Norway	1988-1990	Adult	Unmatched	Uni-Chi Multi-UL	56 IgG+ (O:3) 699 IgG-	Good
Satterthwaite et al. 1999	New Zealand	1988-1993	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni-UL	186 cases 360 controls	Poor
Seuri & Granfors 1992	Finland	1991	Mixed	Cohort Unmatched	Uni-Chi	29 O:3/O:9 233 controls	Good
Skjerve & Kapperud 1991	Norway	1991	Mixed	Matched	Uni-MH	63 cases 123 controls	Good
Tauxe et al., 1987	Belgium	1987	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni-Chi	40 cases ? controls	Good
Wilson et al. 2008	New Zealand	2006	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni-Chi	285 Yersinia 5038 Campylob	Poor

(*) Univariate analysis can be univariate (Uni) and multivariate (Multi) while model can be chi-square (Chi), Mantel-Haenzel (MH), unconditional logistic (UL) and conditional logistic (CL)

3.4.2 *Meta-analysis for host-specific risk factors and travel-, environment-, animal- and food-related pathways of transmission*

In all of the meta-analytical data partitions, there was no effect of the study period on the measured ORs. Said otherwise, there was no evidence that the risks of transmission of yersiniosis have changed significantly in recent years (i.e., after 2000) in the different pathways of exposure under investigation. Since there were only 7 ORs related to the travel risk factor available from the literature, six ORs from Northern Europe and one OR from Oceania, the meta-analysis by geographical region was not performed. The general meta-analysis on these observations revealed that, on average, people who travelled recently had 1.921 (95% CI: 0.692 – 5.333) greater probability of getting infected with yersiniosis than people who did not travel (Table 2). For nationals of Norway, Finland and New Zealand, travelling abroad increased their odds of yersiniosis by an average of 2.257 (95% CI: 0.762 – 6.692). A pooled OR for domestic travelling could not be estimated as there was only one OR in this subcategory. The meta-analysis conducted on the travel data partition suggested the unlikely presence of publication bias ($p=0.371$ in Table 2), while its respective funnel plot showed an acceptable spread of observations, particularly considering the few OR measures available in this partition (Figure 4). No potentially-biased OR was removed after assessing influential observations by Cook's distance.

Table 2. Meta-analysis of travel as a risk factor for yersiniosis for the mixed (n=7 ORs) population – no geographical region removed

Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
All Travel	0.653	0.521	7	[-0.368 – 1.674]	0.209
Fixed effects					
Travel abroad*	0.814	0.554	6	[-0.272 – 1.901]	0.142
Before 2000					0.556
Random effects					
s^2_u (Intercept)	1.0530	QE(df=5)			
s^2 (residual)	2.1206	$p<.0001$			
Publication bias	-0.0002	0.0003			0.371
Points removed	0				

(*) Combining 1 OR from Oceania and 5 ORs from Northern Europe

Figure 4. Funnel plot of the meta-analysis of travel as a risk factor for yersiniosis in the mixed population. The circle marker belong to an OR measure with potential for bias

As in the travel data partition, the number of ORs recovered for the host-specific factors were very few (#9). The meta-analysis on host-specific factors by geographical regions showed differences between Palestine (pooled OR=4.783; $p=0.140$) and Northern Europe (pooled OR=3.2; $p<.0001$; Table 3A), because, in the former, the effect of malnutrition in children was tested, while in the latter, other chronic conditions were evaluated in the mixed population. The general meta-analysis showed that, as a whole, the host-specific factors studied can exacerbate the risk of acquiring yersiniosis with a significant meta-analysed OR of 3.448 (95% CI: 1.446 – 8.215; Table 3B). However, when zooming into the host-specific subcategories, it became clear that, whereas the chronic diseases of thyroid and thalassemia in the mixed population were unlikely to predispose people to acquiring yersiniosis (overall OR=0.791; 95% CI: 0.572 – 1.095), other medical conditions such as malnutrition (in children) and recurrent gastrointestinal problems and previous laparotomy in the mixed population could exacerbate the risk of infection (overall OR=5.176; 95% CI: 3.357 – 7.980; Table 3B). However, we should keep in mind that these results are not conclusive by any means as the available ORs were very few in this data partition. Publication bias was not evident given both the lack of effect of study size on the measured ORs ($p=0.511$), and the acceptable distribution of observations within the funnel plot (Figure 5).

Table 3A. Meta-analyses of host specific factors for yersiniosis by region for the combined mixed (n=5) and children population (n=4)

Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Mixed & Children					
Asia (Palestine)	1.565	1.062	4	[-0.516 – 3.646]	0.140
North Europe	1.166	0.558	5	[0.073 – 2.260]	0.036

Table 3B. Meta-analysis of host specific factors for yersiniosis for the combined mixed (n=5) and children population (n=4) – no geographical region removed

Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
All host specific	1.238	0.443	9	[0.369 – 2.106]	0.005
Fixed effects					
Chronic in mixed	-0.234 ^a	0.166	3	[-0.559 – 0.091]	0.158
Other Med (Mix+Children)	1.644 ^b	0.221	6	[1.211 – 2.077]	<.0001
Before 2000					0.179
Random effects					
s^2_u (Intercept)	0.0000	QE(df=6)		QM(df=2)	
s^2 (residual)	0.0972	p=0.777		p<.0001	
Publication bias	-0.0006	0.0009			0.511
Points removed	1				

Figure 5. Funnel plot of the meta-analysis of host-specific risk factors for yersiniosis in the combined mixed and children population. Circle markers belong to OR measures with potential for bias

Regarding the animal-related pathways of transmission in the combined mixed (31 ORs) and children population (2 ORs), the animal contact routes overall appeared to be an important source of yersiniosis in Northern Europe (pooled OR=1.332; p=0.232), Western Europe (pooled OR=1.733; p=0.146) and Oceania (pooled OR=1.338; p=0.305; Table 4A). When the outcomes from all these regions were combined in the general meta-analysis, animal contact as a whole became significant (p=0.012 in Table 4B) at an overall OR of 1.519 (95% CI: 1.096 – 2.104).

The risk of yersiniosis posed by the occupational animal contact (overall OR=2.071; 95% CI: 1.156 – 3.706) was higher than contact with pets and wild animals, while it did not statistically differ from having direct contact with farm animals (overall OR=1.220; 95% CI: 0.264 – 5.629; Table 4B). It is worthy to mention that, within the mixed population, the occupational exposure data was obtained from farmers dealing with cows, pigs, lambs, poultry and horses. Without overlooking the limited number of OR measures available for contact with pets and wild animals, it was found that having a pet in the household conveyed the same mild risk of infection with *Yersinia enterocolitica* (overall OR=1.368; 95% CI: 0.788 – 2.377) as having contact with birds and mice (overall OR=1.430; 95% CI: 0.819 – 2.499). Applying the Cook's distance diagnostics on the animal contact meta-analysis, one potentially-biased influential OR was removed (Table 4B). In addition, both the formal test for publication bias ($p=0.161$; Table 4B) and the funnel plot (Figure 6) did not indicate any strong evidence of a file-drawer problem for this pathway of exposure.

Table 4A. Meta-analyses of pathways related to animal contact for yersiniosis by region in the mixed (n=31) and children (n=2) population

Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Mixed & Children					
North Europe	0.287	0.240	26	[-0.184 – 0.758]	0.232
Oceania	0.291	0.284	4	[-0.264 – 0.847]	0.305
West Europe	0.550	0.379	3	[-0.192 – 1.293]	0.146

Table 4B. Meta-analysis of pathways related to animal contact for yersiniosis in the combined mixed (n=31) and children (n=2) population – no geographical region removed

Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
All animal	0.418	0.165	33	[0.092 – 0.744]	0.012
Fixed effects					
Farm	0.199 ^{ab}	0.780	7	[-1.330 – 1.728]	0.799
Occupational	0.728 ^{bc}	0.297	17	[0.145 – 1.310]	0.014
Pets*	0.314 ^a	0.281	6	[-0.238 – 0.866]	0.264
Wild	0.358 ^a	0.285	3	[-0.200 – 0.916]	0.209
Before 2000					0.254
Random effects					
s^2_u (Intercept)	0.0131	QE(df=28)		QM(df=4)	
s^2 (residual)	0.2658	p=0.273		p=0.090	
Publication bias	-0.0002	0.0001			0.161
Points removed	1				

(*) In children (2 ORs) and mixed (4 ORs)

Figure 6. Funnel plot of the meta-analysis of animal contact pathways as risk factors for yersiniosis in the combined mixed and children population. Circle markers belong to OR measures with potential for bias

In general, the combined environmental pathways were strongly associated with yersiniosis, in the geographical regions in which more data were available: Palestine (pooled OR=2.459, $p=0.034$) and Northern Europe (pooled OR=1.690, $p=0.027$; Table 5A). The data available for Oceania and Western Europe were so few that no association could be proven. Taking all the geographical regions together, the general meta-analysis demonstrated the relevance of the environmental pathways in the transmission of yersiniosis in the mixed population (overall OR=1.672; 95% CI: 1.332 – 2.096; Table 5B).

Table 5A. Meta-analyses of environmental pathways for yersiniosis by region for the combined mixed ($n=9$) and children ($n=12$) population

Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Mixed & Children					
Asia (Palestine)	0.900	0.424	7	[0.069 – 1.731]	0.034
North Europe	0.525	0.240	10	[0.055 – 0.996]	0.028
Oceania	0.345	0.381	2	[-0.401 – 1.092]	0.365
West Europe	0.278	0.375	2	[-0.456 – 1.012]	0.457

On meta-analysis by environmental subcategory, the lowest association with yersiniosis was borne by the exposure of living on a rural environment (overall OR=1.165; 95% CI: 0.610 – 2.228; Table 5B) which was comparable in magnitude with the exposure of contact with farm animals (overall OR=1.220; Table 4B). The mixed population that drank well water, untreated water or water from a non-chlorinated water supply (drink water, overall OR=1.766; 95% CI: 1.231 – 2.537) were as exposed to yersiniosis as children playing in a sandbox or use of a baby’s dummy (playground, overall OR=1.582; 95% CI: 0.985 – 2.542; Table 5B). The highest pooled OR was found for the environmental pathway of “waste water” as yersiniosis

source (overall OR=2.248; 95% CI: 1.500 – 3.370), which comprised the exposures of non-reticulated sewage and contact with human fecal matter. After Cook’s distance assessment, no potentially-biased OR was found to be influential (Table 5B). In addition, the OR measures appeared to be very well distributed within the funnel area (Figure 7). Thus, the formal test for publication bias failed to find any dependence of OR measures upon study size (p=0.290; Table 5B).

Table 5B. Meta-analyses of environmental pathways for yersiniosis for the combined mixed (n=9) and children (n=12) population – no geographical region removed

Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
All environment	0.514	0.115	21	[0.287 – 0.740]	<.0001
Fixed effects					
Drink water	0.569 ^b	0.184	10	[0.208 – 0.931]	0.002
Farm	0.153 ^a	0.330	3	[-0.494 – 0.801]	0.642
Playground*	0.459 ^b	0.242	5	[-0.015 – 0.933]	0.058
Waste water	0.810 ^c	0.236	3	[0.347 – 1.272]	0.001
Before 2000					0.973
Random effects					
s ² _u (Intercept)	0.0879	QE(df=17)		QM(df=4)	
s ² (residual)	0.2239	p=0.078		p=0.001	
Publication bias	-0.0001	0.0001			0.290
Points removed	0				

(*) Comprising use of a baby’s dummy and children playing in a sandbox

Figure 7. Funnel plot of the meta-analysis of environmental pathways as risk factors for yersiniosis in the combined mixed and children population. Circle markers belong to OR measures with potential for bias

Most of the information on routes of transmission of yersiniosis was recovered for different foodstuffs, which amounted to 85 OR measures. The meta-analysis by geographical region showed that the highest associations between yersiniosis and food consumption were posed by Western Europe in both the mixed (pooled OR=3.274; p=0.143) and the children (pooled OR=5.212; p<.0001) populations (Table 6A). Whilst in case-control studies from Northern Europe, food was overall a potential determinant of yersiniosis in both the mixed (pooled OR=1.798, p=0.363) and the children population (pooled OR=1.900; p=0.013), in the case-control studies from Oceania, food vehicles overall appeared to be a non-significant source of yersiniosis (pooled OR=0.993; p=0.995; Table 6A).

Table 6A. Meta-analyses of food pathways for yersiniosis by region for mixed (n=70) and children (n=15) population

Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Mixed					
North Europe	0.587	0.645	42	[-0.676 – 1.851]	0.363
Oceania	-0.007	1.072	13	[-2.107 – 2.093]	0.995
West Europe	1.186	0.808	15	[-0.400 – 2.770]	0.143
Children					
North Europe	0.642	0.259	12	[0.135 – 1.149]	0.013
West Europe	1.651	0.276	3	[1.110 – 2.192]	<.0001

The general meta-analyses on food demonstrated that, as a whole, food from different classes, could act as potential determinants of yersiniosis in the mixed population (overall OR=1.770; 95% CI: 0.967 – 3.238) and – to a greater degree – in the children population (overall OR=3.121; 95% CI: 1.550 – 6.271 in Table 6B). At this broader data partition, meta-analysis made it possible to establish which food categories were more or less associated with yersiniosis. In the mixed population, produce which were made up basically of fruits, vegetables, roots and seeds (overall OR=1.210; 95% CI: 0.664 – 2.208) had the lowest association with yersiniosis. At a slightly higher association level laid the composite type of foods (overall OR=1.324; 95% CI: 0.765 – 2.298). Meat bore the highest association with yersiniosis in the mixed population: on meta-analysis, people with yersiniosis were more likely to have consumed contaminated meats (overall OR=1.868; 95% CI: 1.090 – 3.200) than healthy controls. In the food data partition for the children population, data was only available for meats. Thus, children who consumed contaminated foods (in this case meat) presented overall 3.121 times (95% CI: 1.550 – 6.271) greater probability of acquiring yersiniosis than those who did not. After Cook's distance assessment, two potentially-biased OR popped up as influential points in the mixed population meta-analysis, and hence, they were removed from the data set (Table 7B). In both meta-analyses, the case-control study size had an effect on the measured ORs. The same evidence of publication bias could be attested from the asymmetrical funnel plots (Figure 8). It is likely that when the associations between yersiniosis and foodstuffs were found to be weak or non-significant in the case-control studies, they were omitted from the results tables or even from being published altogether.

Table 6B. Meta-analyses of food pathways for yersiniosis in the mixed (n=65) and children (n=15) population – no geographical region removed

Pop	Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Mixed	All foods	0.571	0.308	65	[-0.034 – 1.175]	0.064
	Fixed effects					
	Composite	0.281 ^b	0.287	10	[-0.268 – 0.832]	0.314
	Meat	0.625 ^c	0.274	43	[0.086 – 1.163]	0.023
	Produce	0.191 ^a	0.307	12	[-0.409 – 0.792]	0.533
	Before 2000					0.278
	Random effects					
	s^2_u (Intercept)	0.3744	QE(df=60)		QM(df=3)	
	s^2 (residual)	0.5993	p<.0001		p<.0001	
	Publication bias	-0.0004	0.0001			0.003
Points removed	2					
Children	All foods	1.138	0.357	15	[0.438 – 1.836]	0.001
	Fixed effects					
	Meat	1.138	0.357	15	[0.438 – 1.836]	0.001
	Before 2000					ND
	Random effects					
	s^2_u (Intercept)	0.2298	QE(df=14)			
	s^2 (residual)	0.6195	p=0.001			
	Publication bias	-0.0021	0.0008			0.010
	Points removed	0				

Figure 8. Funnel plots of the meta-analyses of food pathways for acquiring yersiniosis in the mixed (left) and children population (right). Circle markers belong to OR measures with potential for bias

Within meats, the meta-analysis by geographical region showed that, as in the all-foods data partition, the overall association between yersiniosis and consumption of meat in the mixed population was the greatest in the case-control studies from Western Europe (pooled OR=3.522; p=0.107), followed by those of Northern Europe (pooled OR=1.778; p=0.357 in Table 7A). The trend was the same in the children population, although with higher pooled ORs, correspondingly (Table 7A).

In the mixed population, beef (overall OR=0.944; 95% CI: 0.871 – 1.021), other red meats – encompassing venison, lamb, sheep and game meat (overall OR=0.980; 95% CI: 0.897 – 1.069), and processed meats – including pork cold cuts, sausages, bacon, ham and salami (overall OR=1.033; 95% CI: 0.969 – 1.095) posed the lowest associations, if any, with yersiniosis (Table 7B). Slightly higher associations with disease in the mixed population were found for poultry meat (overall OR=1.091; 95% CI: 0.974 – 1.223) as well as other meats, encompassing kebab meat and meats of non-specific origin (overall OR=1.310; 95% CI: 0.893 – 1.921). Among the meat subcategories, the greatest association with yersiniosis was borne by pork. The meta-analysis of 15 OR measures of different kinds of pork preparations revealed that, in the mixed population, those who ate pork had 1.988 times (95% CI: 1.787 – 2.212; Table 7B) greater probability of becoming infected with yersiniosis than those who did not consume pork in any of its forms. The meta-analysis conducted on the children data partition of meats showed that children were on average more susceptible of acquiring yersiniosis from consuming pork (overall OR=3.418; 95% CI: 1.893 – 6.166) than the mixed population. After pork, the processed meat category, which included ham, sausages and pate, represented also a significant source of yersiniosis in children (overall OR=2.450; 95% CI: 1.232 – 4.870 in Table 7B).

Table 7A. Meta-analyses of meat consumption related pathways for yersiniosis by region for the mixed (n=43) and the children population (n=15)

Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Mixed					
North Europe	0.577	0.624	23	[-0.649 – 1.800]	0.357
Oceania	0.032	1.033	8	[-1.992 – 2.056]	0.975
West Europe	1.259	0.782	12	[-0.274 – 2.792]	0.107
Children					
North Europe	0.642	0.259	12	[0.135 – 1.149]	0.013
West Europe	1.651	0.276	3	[1.110 – 2.192]	<.0001

The forest plots of separate meta-analyses conducted on the association between consumption of pork and yersiniosis are shown in Figure 9 (for the mixed population) and Figure 10 (for the children population). Because of the significant between-study heterogeneity (i.e., variability in extracted ORs), the random-effects solution is presented in these plots. In the meta-analysis for the mixed population, one potentially-biased point was removed for being influential, while in meta-analysis for the children population, no potentially-biased ORs was

found to be influential (Table 7B). According to the formal test of study size effect (Table 7B), the presence of publication bias in the mixed population is unlikely ($p=0.342$) while the opposite is true in the children population ($p=0.020$ in Table 7B). However, the funnel plots of these meta-analyses displayed an acceptable distribution of the extracted ORs (Figure 11).

Table 7B. Meta-analyses of meat consumption related pathways for yersiniosis in the mixed (n=43) and children population (n=15) – no region was removed

Pop	Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Mixed	Fixed effects					
	Beef	-0.058 ^a	0.041	6	[-0.138 – 0.021]	0.150
	Other red meat	-0.020 ^a	0.045	7	[-0.109 – 0.067]	0.642
	Others	0.270 ^b	0.195	5	[-0.113 – 0.653]	0.170
	Pork	0.687 ^c	0.054	15	[0.581 – 0.794]	<.0001
	Poultry	0.087 ^{ab}	0.058	3	[-0.026 – 0.201]	0.132
	Proc meat	0.033 ^a	0.032	7	[-0.031 – 0.091]	0.314
	Before 2000					0.217
	Random effects					
	s^2_u (Intercept)	0.0000	QE(df=36)		QM(df=6)	
	s^2 (residual)	0.5278	p<.0001		p<.0001	
	Publication bias	-0.0001	0.0001		0.342	
Points removed	1					
Children	Fixed effects					
	Pork	1.229 ^b	0.301	8	[0.638 – 1.819]	<.0001
	Proc meat	0.896 ^a	0.350	7	[0.209 – 1.583]	0.011
	Before 2000					ND
	Random effects					
	s^2_u (Intercept)		QE(df=13)		QM(df=2)	
	s^2 (residual)		p=0.010		p=0.002	
	Publication bias	-0.0019	0.0008		0.020	
	Points removed	0				

Figure 9. Forest plot of the meta-analysis conducted on the association between sporadic yersiniosis in the mixed population and the consumption of pork meat, as measured by the odds-ratio parameterisation

Figure 10. Forest plot of the meta-analysis conducted on the association between sporadic yersiniosis in children and the consumption of pork meat, as measured by the odds-ratio parameterisation

Figure 11. Funnel plots of the meta-analyses of meat consumption pathways for yersiniosis in the mixed (left) and children population (right). Circle markers belong to OR measures with potential for bias

In the questionnaires presented to cases and controls, previous consumption of eggs, milk and dairy products, beverages and seafood was seldom enquired. For this reason, meta-analyses could not be conducted on the above disaggregated categories. Most of the data pertaining to produce were extracted from Northern European case-control studies (11 ORs) while only one OR was extracted from a case-control study from New Zealand. Hence, no meta-analysis by geographical region was carried out. Among the food classes, for which data was available – meat, composite foods and produce – the latter turned out to be the most innocuous in terms of acting as a vehicle of transmission of yersiniosis. Both fruits (overall OR=0.992; 95% CI: 0.988 – 0.996) and vegetables (overall OR=0.644; 95% CI: 0.443 – 0.938) were not associated with disease, while the consumption of roots and legumes (soybean) presented an overall OR only marginally higher than 1.0 (overall OR=1.078; 95% CI: 0.729 – 1.597 in Table 9). In this meta-analysis, no potentially-biased OR was influential, and publication bias was not evident either from the formal test of study size ($p=0.345$ in Table 8) or from the funnel plot (Figure 12).

Table 8. Meta-analysis of produce related pathways for yersiniosis in the mixed (n=12) population – no geographical region removed (11 North Europe + 1 Oceania)

Pop	Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Mixed	Fixed effects					
	Fruits	-0.008 ^a	0.002	5	[-0.012 – -0.004]	0.001
	Roots&Legu	0.076 ^b	0.200	4	[-0.316 – 0.468]	0.703
	Vegetables	-0.439 ^a	0.191	3	[-0.814 – -0.064]	0.022
	Before 2000					0.529
	Random effects					
	s^2_u (Intercept)	0.0000	QE(df=9)		QM(df=3)	
	s^2 (residual)	0.2603	p=0.140		p=0.001	
	Publication bias	-0.0006	0.0006			0.345
	Points removed	0				

Figure 12. Funnel plot of the meta-analysis of produce consumption pathways for yersiniosis infection in the mixed population. The circle marker belongs to an OR measure with potential for bias

Composite foods constituted an important source of yersiniosis, particularly in the Northern European case-control studies (pooled OR=1.744; p=0.001 in Table 9A). Due to the limited number of extracted ORs, no geographical region was removed for the general meta-analysis by composite classes. On meta-analysis, people with yersiniosis were on average 1.357 (95% CI: 0.797 – 2.314) times more likely to have consumed any multi-ingredient dishes than controls. The level of risk associated to composite fast-food was significantly lower than that of composite dishes at a pooled OR of 1.227 (95% CI: 0.984 – 1.531) (Table 9B). In the funnel plot, the few observations available appeared well dispersed within the funnel's area, although the formal test evidenced some publication bias (p=0.001 in Table 9B). No potentially-biased OR turned out to be influential in the regression.

Table 9A. Meta-analysis of composite-food related pathways for yersiniosis by geographical region for the mixed (n=9) population

Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Mixed					
North Europe	0.556	0.157	6	[0.248 – 0.864]	0.001
West Europe	-0.135	0.063	3	[-0.260 – -0.011]	0.033

Table 9B. Meta-analysis of composite-food related pathways for yersiniosis in the mixed (n=10) population – no region was removed

Pop	Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Mixed	Fixed effects					
	Dishes eaten out	0.305 ^b	0.272	6	[-0.227 – 0.839]	0.261
	Fast-food	0.205 ^a	0.113	4	[-0.016 – 0.426]	0.069
	Before 2000					0.155
	Random effects					
	s^2_u (Intercept)	0.2080	QE(df=8)		QM(df=2)	
	s^2 (residual)	0.5459	p<.0001		p=0.042	
	Publication bias	-0.0006	0.0002			0.001
	Points removed	0				

Figure 13. Funnel plot of the meta-analysis of composite food consumption pathways for yersiniosis in the mixed population. The circle marker belongs to an OR measure with potential for bias

3.4.3 Meta-analysis on the risk of yersiniosis by ready-to-eat foods

Limited data was available for RTE foods as pathways of exposure for human yersiniosis. The eight OR measures that could be extracted belonged to processed meats such as ham, RTE sausages, salami and patê. The meta-analysis undertaken on these ORs indicated that there is no evidence for meat-based RTE foods to be regarded as potential vehicles of transmission of yersiniosis (overall OR=1.075; 95% CI: 0.849 – 1.363). In this data partition, there was no potentially-biased OR, while results of the formal test for publication bias implied that the larger the case-control study size, the smaller the OR that was measured ($p=0.044$; Table 10). Hence, it is possible that low-powered studies failing to find a significant OR due to consumption of any RTE food had remained unpublished. However, the even spread of data points within the funnel plot (Figure 14) does not hint any strong file-drawer problem.

Table 10. Meta-analysis of the risk of yersiniosis due to consumption of RTE foods in the combined mixed ($n=5$) and children ($n=3$) population. No geographical region was removed

Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Fixed effects					
Meat-based*	0.073	0.121	8	[-0.164 – 0.310]	0.546
Before 2000					0.731
Random effects					
s^2_u (Intercept)	0.0337	QE(df=7)			
s^2 (residual)	0.1840	$p=0.014$			
Publication bias	-0.0002	0.0001			0.044
Points removed	0				

(*) All data belonged to processed meat

Figure 14. Funnel plot of the meta-analysis of consumption of meat-based RTE foods as a risk factor for yersiniosis

The main results from the meta-analyses on risk factors and pathways of exposure were compiled in two forest plots: one forest plot was designed for comparing the association with yersiniosis among the *global* risk categories (Figure 15) and the other forest plot for comparing among the *disaggregated* categories (Figure 16). To visually distinguish the most important routes of transmission, the pooled ORs listed in the forest plots were ranked by mean's decreasing order, and to assess the reliability in the pooled ORs, the number of observations used in the computations were also shown.

Among the global risk categories that were amenable to be meta-analysed, the host-specific factors, made up of chronic diseases in the mixed population and malnutrition in children, represented as a whole the most important risk factor for acquiring yersiniosis in the mixed population (overall OR=3.45; 95% CI: 1.45 – 8.22), immediately followed by travel (overall OR=1.92; 95% CI: 0.69 – 5.33; Figure 15). In the mixed population (as evaluated by the mixed only or the combined mixed/children partitions), the consumption of meat was more important a vehicle of transmission of yersiniosis than the environmental (overall OR=1.67; 95% CI: 1.33 – 2.10) and the animal-related pathways (overall OR=1.52; 95% CI: 1.10 – 2.10) pathways of infection. Nonetheless, children were more susceptible of acquiring yersiniosis from meat consumption (overall OR=3.12; 95% CI: 1.55 – 6.28) than the mixed population. The global routes of exposure that on meta-analysis had weak (pooled OR marginally higher than one) or non-significant association with yersiniosis in the mixed population were: composite foods (overall OR=1.32; 95% CI: 0.76 – 2.29), produce (overall OR=1.21; 95% CI: 0.85 – 1.36) and RTE meats (overall OR=1.08; 95% CI: 0.85 – 1.36 in Figure 15).

Exploring the disaggregated risk factors ranked by mean pooled OR (Figure 16), it became evident that medical conditions such as having a laparotomy or a recurrent gastrointestinal condition in the mixed population or malnutrition in children constituted the most important risk factors predisposing the acquisition of yersiniosis (overall OR=5.18; 95% CI: 3.36 – 7.98). International travel (overall OR=2.26; 95% CI: 0.76 – 6.69), lack of wastewater treatment (overall OR=2.25; 95% CI: 1.41 – 3.57) and farmer's occupational exposure to food-producing animals (overall OR=2.07; 95% CI: 1.16 – 3.71) turned out to be as important

sources of yersiniosis as the consumption of pork meat (overall OR=1.99; 95% CI: 1.79 – 2.21). Drinking untreated water bore significantly higher association with yersiniosis (overall OR=1.77; 95% CI: 1.23 – 2.53) than the animal pathways of contact with birds/mice (overall OR=1.43; 95% CI: 0.82 – 2.50), pets (overall OR=1.37; 95% CI: 0.79 – 2.39) and farm animals (overall OR=1.22; 95% CI: 0.26 – 5.63). Overall, living on a farm (overall OR=1.17; 95% CI: 0.61 – 2.23) had a comparable low association with yersiniosis than having contact with farm animals. The disaggregated food classes that were likely to have a very mild or marginal association with yersiniosis (OR>1.0) were: dishes eaten out (overall OR=1.36; 95% CI: 0.80 – 2.31), other (non-specified) meats (overall OR=1.31; 95% CI: 0.89 – 1.92), fast-food (overall OR=1.23; 95% CI: 0.98 – 1.53), poultry (overall OR= 1.09; 95% CI: 0.97 – 1.22), roots/legumes (overall OR=1.08; 95% CI: 0.73 – 1.60) and processed meats (overall OR=1.03; 95% CI: 0.97 – 1.10).

Figure 15. Forest plot summarising overall odds-ratios of acquiring yersiniosis for global risk categories, ranked by mean pooled OR decreasing order.

Figure 16. Forest plot summarising overall odds-ratios of acquiring yersiniosis for disaggregated risk categories, ranked in decreasing order. The disaggregated risk categories presented are only those made up of at least n=3 ORs

In the mixed population, fruits (overall OR=0.99; 95% CI: 0.99 – 1.00), beef (overall OR=0.94; 95% CI: 0.87 – 1.02), other red meats (overall OR=0.98; 95% CI: 0.90 – 1.07) and vegetables (overall OR=0.64; 95% CI: 0.44 – 0.94) did not appear to act as vehicles of infection with yersiniosis. In the children population, sufficient data were available for only three disaggregated risk categories, and hence could be meta-analysed (Figure 16). The three of them were significantly associated with yersiniosis, and they were ranked as: consumption of pork (overall OR=3.42; 95% CI: 1.89 – 6.17), consumption to processed meat (overall OR=2.45; 95% CI: 1.23 – 4.87) and exposure to playground (overall OR=1.58; 95% CI: 0.99 – 2.54) (Figure 16).

3.4.4 Meta-analysis on the effects of handling on the risk of transmission of yersiniosis by food consumption

For *Y. enterocolitica*, the effects of setting (i.e., home, eating out) on the risk of transmission of disease could not be appraised because of lack of data. Information on food handling (i.e., raw, undercooked) was barely reported in case-control studies, except for the food classes of pork and other meats. Thus, both food classes were merged into a single class, and a meta-analysis model to determine the effects of eating raw and undercooked meat was adjusted. Full estimates and the corresponding funnel plot are shown in the supplementary Table S1 and Figure S1.

On average, people who reported having eaten *undercooked* pork or other undercooked meats had 2.945 (95% CI: 2.380 – 3.640; Table 11) greater probability of acquiring yersiniosis than those who stated having consumed simply pork or other meats (without being specific as to whether it was raw or undercooked; this is, the base scenario). However, those who consumed *raw* pork or other raw meats were at a significantly greater risk, as they had their odds of acquiring yersiniosis increased by a factor of 3.869 (95% CI: 2.130 – 7.029) times that of the base scenario.

Table 11. Meta-analysed effects of handling on the base OR of yersiniosis from consumption of pork (n=23) and other meats (n=6)

Food class	Estimate	Mean	2.5 th percentile	97.5 th percentile
Pork and other meats	OR(Base)	1.263	0.931	1.714
	OR(Raw)/OR(Base)	3.869 ^a	2.130	7.029
	OR(Undercooked)/OR(Base)	2.945 ^b	2.380	3.640

3.4.5 *Synthesis of the risks associated to ways of preparation and poor handling of foods*

The forest plot of Figure 17 compiles all the exposures related to food preparation and poor handling practices, which were examined in case-control studies as potential risk factors for sporadic yersiniosis. Food preparation practices such as using a wooden chopping board and rapidly thawing meat were not found to increase the risk of acquiring yersiniosis. On the other hand, cleaning utensils after use was not either proven to have a protective effect. However, poor handling habits related to rarely washing vegetables and roots were shown to boost the transmission of *Y. enterocolitica* in the mixed population with ORs between 1.35 and 4.23.

Figure 17. Forest plot of the odds-ratios of acquiring yersiniosis associated to food preparation and poor handling practices

4 Conclusions

4.4 Meta-analysis on risk factors for sporadic yersiniosis

- ❖ The outcomes from 14 case-control studies investigating routes of exposure for sporadic yersiniosis were meta-analysed, taking into account geographical region and period of study.
- ❖ Very limited or no data were available for categories such as recreational water, use of antibiotics, use of antacids, chronic diseases, and consumption of eggs, beverages, grains, seafood and dairy. Hence, the significance of these sources as potential vehicles of transmission of yersiniosis could not be appraised.
- ❖ The medical conditions of recurrent gastrointestinal conditions and laparotomy in the mixed population, and malnutrition in children were the most important factors predisposing the acquisition of yersiniosis (OR=5.18), followed by international travel (OR=2.26) in the mixed population.
- ❖ Lack of wastewater treatment (OR=2.25) and occupational exposure to animals by farmers (OR=2.07) turned out to be, at least, as important sources of yersiniosis as the most known exposure of pork meat consumption (OR=1.99) in the mixed population.
- ❖ In the mixed population, drinking untreated water bore higher association with yersiniosis (OR=1.77) than the animal-related routes of contact with wild animals (OR=1.43), pets (OR=1.37) and farm animals (OR=1.22).
- ❖ In the children population, the amount of data extracted allowed adjusting meta-analysis models only on three risk categories. These were ranked as: consumption of pork (OR=3.42), consumption of processed meat (OR=2.45) and exposure to playground (OR=1.58).
- ❖ In the mixed population, the food classes that had a minor or marginal association with yersiniosis (OR<1.0) were: dishes eaten out (OR=1.36), other (non-specified) meats (OR=1.31), fast-food (OR=1.23), poultry (OR= 1.09), roots/legumes (OR=1.08) and processed meats (OR=1.03).
- ❖ Routes of exposure that on meta-analysis were seemingly not vehicles of yersiniosis in the mixed population were: fruits (OR=0.99), beef (OR=0.94), other red meats (OR=0.98) and vegetables (OR=0.64).
- ❖ In comparison to people who reported having eaten *simply* pork (or other meats), people who ate *undercooked* pork (or other undercooked meats) had their odds of infection with yersiniosis increased by 2.945 times, while those who consumed *raw* pork (or other raw meats) were at a significantly greater probability of acquiring yersiniosis of 3.869 times that of the base scenario.

5. References

5.4 Fourteen case-control studies for *Yersinia enterocolitica*

- [Boqvist et al., 2009] Boqvist, S., Pettersson, H., Svensson, A., and Andersson, Y. (2009). Sources of sporadic *Yersinia enterocolitica* infection in children in Sweden, 2004: a case-control study. *Epidemiology and Infection*, 137(6):897–905.
- [Cherchi et al., 1995] Cherchi, G., Pacifico, L., Cossellu, S., Gallisai, D., Zanetti, S., Fadda, G., and Chiesa, C. (1995). Prospective study of *Yersinia enterocolitica* infection in thalassemic patients. *Pediatric Infectious Disease Journal*, 14(7):579–583.
- [Hansen et al., 2006] Hansen, P. S., Wenzel, B. E., Brix, T. H., and Hegedus, L. (2006). *Yersinia enterocolitica* infection does not confer an increased risk of thyroid antibodies: evidence from a Danish twin study. *Clinical and Experimental Immunology*, 146(1):32–38.
- [Huovinen et al., 2010] Huovinen, E., Sihvonen, L., Virtanen, M., Haukka, K., Siitonen, A., and Kuusi, M. (2010). Symptoms and sources of *Yersinia enterocolitica*-infection: A case-control study. *BMC Infectious Diseases*, 10(122):1–9.
- [Ostroff et al., 1994] Ostroff, S., Kapperud, G., Hutwagner, L., Nesbakken, T., Bean, N., Lassen, J., and Tauxe, R. (1994). Sources of sporadic *yersinia-enterocolitica* infections in norway - A prospective case-control study. *Epidemiology and Infection*, 112(1):133–141.
- [Ostroff et al., 1992] Ostroff, S., Kapperud, G., Lassen, J., Aasen, S., and Tauxe, R. (1992). Clinical-features of sporadic *Yersinia enterocolitica* infections in Norway. *Journal of Infectious Diseases*, 166(4):812–817.
- [Qouqa et al., 2011] Qouqa, I. A. E., Jarou, M. A. E., Samaha, A. S. A., Afifi, A. S. A., and Jarousha, A. M. K. A. (2011). *Yersinia enterocolitica* infection among children aged less than 12 years: a case-control study. *International Journal of Infectious Diseases*, 15(1):e48 – e53.
- [Rosner et al., 2012] Rosner, B., Stark, K., Höhle, M., and Werber, D. (2012). Risk factors for sporadic *Yersinia enterocolitica* infections, Germany 2009-2010. *Epidemiology and Infection*, 140(10):1738–1747.
- [Saebo et al., 1994] Saebo, A., Kapperud, G., Lassen, J., and Waage, J. (1994). Prevalence of antibodies to *yersinia-enterocolitica* 0-3 among norwegian military recruits - association with risk factors and clinical manifestations. *European Journal of Epidemiology*, 10(6):749–755.
- [Satterthwaite et al., 1999] Satterthwaite, P., Pritchard, K., Floyd, D., and Law, B. (1999). A case-control study of *Yersinia enterocolitica* infections in Auckland. *Australian and New Zealand Journal of Public Health*, 23(5):482–485.

[Seuri and Granfors, 1992] Seuri, M. and Granfors, K. (1992). Possible confounders of the relationship between occupational swine contact and *Yersinia enterocolitica* 0:3 and 0:9 antibodies. *European Journal of Epidemiology*, 8(4):532–538.

[Skjerve and Kapperud, 1991] Skjerve, E. and Kapperud, G. (1991). *Epidemiology of Human Yersinia Enterocolitica, Campylobacter jejuni coli and Salmonella Typhimurium* 0:4, 12 Infections in Norway. International Symposia on Veterinary Epidemiology and Economics proceedings, ISVEE 6: *Proceedings of the 6th International Symposium on Veterinary Epidemiology and Economics*, Ottawa, Canada, Public health session, pp 568-570, Aug 1991

[Tauxe et al., 1987] Tauxe, R. V., Wauters, G., Goossens, V., Noyen, R. V., Vandepitte, J., Martin, S. M., Mol, P. D., and Thiers, G. (1987). *Yersinia enterocolitica* infections and pork: The missing link. *The Lancet*, 329(8542):1129 – 1132.

[Wilson et al., 2008] Wilson, N., Baker, M., Edwards, R., and Simmons, G. (2008). Case-case analysis of enteric diseases with routine surveillance data: Potential use and example results. *Epidemiologic Perspectives and Innovations*, 5(1):1–8.

4 Supplementary table and figure of the effects of handling on the transmission of yersiniosis

Table S1. Meta-analysis of the effects of handling and setting on the risk of STEC infection by consumption of pork (n=23) and other meats (n=6)

Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Fixed effects					
Handl: Base	0.234	0.155	14	[-0.071 – 0.539]	0.132
Handl: Raw	1.353 ^b	0.304	5	[0.756 – 1.950]	<.0001
Handl: Undercooked	1.080 ^a	0.109	10	[0.867 – 1.292]	<.0001
Random effects					
s^2_u (Intercept)	0.0325		QE(df=26)	QM(df=2)	
s^2 (residual)	0.6292		p=0.004	p<.0001	
Publication bias	0.0000	0.0001			0.551
Points removed	0				

Figure S1. Funnel plot of the meta-analysis of the effects of handling and setting on the risk of yersiniosis by consumption of pork and other meats. Circle markers belong to OR measures with potential for bias